

MOLECULAR STATE OF DISSOLVED SHELLAC

BY SADHAN BASU

A systematic study of the viscometric properties of shellac in different solvents and at different temperatures has been made. It has been found that shellac dissolves molecularly in ethyl alcohol, *n*-propyl alcohol, *n*-butyl alcohol, *n*-butyric acid and ethyl lactate, at least at low concentrations of the solute. Water causes solvation of shellac in solution. In concentrated solution a definite but loose structure develops. Shellac gels show the phenomenon of gel syneresis.

Systematic investigations on the nature of shellac solutions undertaken by Palit (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 537) revealed, from considerations of dialysis, ultrafiltration, etc., that the previous views of Gardner (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1923, 21, 227; *ibid. Anal. Ed.*, 1929, 1, 207) and of Verman (London Shellac Research Bureau, Technical paper No. 11, pp. 4, 11) regarding the colloidal nature of shellac solution could not be wholly justified. Shellac, Palit believed, dissolved molecularly in organic solvents, the observed gelation of the solution at a particular concentration and temperature being explained on the basis of solvation. He, however, did not produce any direct experimental evidence in support of the existence of solvation. With a view to throwing further light on the problem, an entirely new line of investigation, namely, a systematic study of the viscometric properties of shellac in different solvents and at different temperatures was undertaken, the results of which have been reported in the present paper.

The relation between the viscosity and the concentration of the dissolved macromolecular particles, first deduced by Einstein (*Ann. Physik*, 1906, *iv*, 19, 289) for rigid spheres, may be stated as

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + 2.5 \phi \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

where ϕ is the ratio of the volume of the dissolved solute to that of the solvent and η , η_0 are respectively the viscosity of the solution and viscosity of the solvent. Putting η/η_0 as η_{rel} (relative viscosity) and $\eta_{rel} - 1$ as η_{sp} (specific viscosity), equation (1) may be written as

$$\eta_{sp} = 2.5 \phi \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

The most general form of this equation, irrespective of particle shape, is

$$\eta_{sp} = k\phi \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

where k is a constant depending on the shape of the particle. Now ϕ is proportional to concentration, hence if η_{sp}/c be plotted against c , the curve should be parallel to the concentration axis, at least in the region of ideal dispersion. In most cases of macromolecular solutions, however, this parallelism is never realised, the curve showing a constant rise with concentration. Kraemer (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1935, 39, 153), however, showed that if

the curve η_{sp}/c against c be extrapolated to zero concentration, the intercept on η_{sp}/c axis is a quantity characteristic of macromolecular solute in its dissolved state. This quantity, called by Kraemer, intrinsic viscosity, $[\eta]$, is defined as

$$[\eta] = (\eta_{sp}/c) = 0 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad 4)$$

The intrinsic viscosity is very sensitive to changes in size, shape, aggregation, solvation, etc. of the particles. The degree of solvation, as also aggregation, decrease with rising temperature and consequently intrinsic viscosity may be expected to decrease with temperature. Thus from the effect of temperature on intrinsic viscosity, the physical nature of the solute in the solution can be deduced and a clear insight into the nature of the solution obtained.

Further, from the literature on the subject, it is found that solutions of high polymers show very large deviation from the classical Hagen-Poiseuille law for the flow of liquids through capillaries, for which other things remaining constant, the volume discharged in unit time through a capillary, instead of being simply proportional to pressure, increases more rapidly with increasing pressure. Two types of deviations have been observed. In one type, the liquids deviate more and more from Newtonian behaviour as the pressure is increased, and in the other, they tend to conform more and more to Newtonian behaviour under the same circumstances. Both these effects have been attributed to the existence of some sort of structure in the solution. In fact, the effect of velocity gradient on viscosity is one of the most definite indications as to the state of dispersion of the dissolved units.

EXPERIMENTAL

Apparatus and Method.— Dewaxed shellac was powdered to 100 mesh, dried at 42° for 6 hours and then kept in a vacuum desiccator over fused calcium chloride for 4 days. The same sample was used in each experiment, since the moisture content and the state of aggregation have great influence on the viscosity of shellac, especially in dilute solutions. The solvents used were thoroughly dried and twice distilled with the usual precautions.

Viscosity measurements were carried out with an Ostwald's capillary viscometer, temperature being controlled by means of a water thermostat.

Solutions were prepared by weighing out the dried shellac in conical flasks and adding the required volume of solvents from a burette. The flasks were well corked and the mixture allowed to stand 4 hours for complete dissolution. The solutions were then rapidly filtered and kept in tightly corked bottles.

The effects of different amounts of shearing stress were observed with a Bingham capillary viscometer, the pressure being applied by means of a water column. In between the viscometer and the water column was placed a calcium chloride guard tube in order to prevent entrance of moisture.

Measurements of density were carried out with a pycnometer and the partial specific volume was calculated from the equation,

$$V = \frac{w - (l - h)}{\rho h}$$

where V is the weight of the solvent in the pycnometer, l , the weight of solution, h , the weight of solute and ρ , the density of solvent.

Intrinsic Viscosity and Solvent.—The variation of η_{sp}/c with c for solvents is shown in Fig. 1. The measurements were made up to 4% concentration of shellac, since within this range the $\eta_{sp} - c$ curve is strictly linear and the partial specific volume remains substantially constant (Table I).

TABLE I

Shellac (%)	...	1	2	3	4
Partial sp. vol.(c.c.)	...	0.930	0.928	0.933	0.932

Thus from the observed linearity of η_{sp}/c curve, as well as from the constancy of the partial specific volume, the solution within this range may be taken as strictly dilute. Though a straight line relationship has been observed for all the solvents used (Fig. 1), the curve $\eta_{sp}/c - c$ is not parallel to the c -axis. For three different alcohols (viz., ethyl, n -propyl and n -butyl),

Fig. 1.

the curves are nearly parallel to each other, but in the case of n -butyric

acid the slope is much steeper. The values of intrinsic viscosity, as obtained from an extrapolation of the curves to zero concentration, are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Solvent.	$[\eta]$.	Solvent.	$[\eta]$.
Ethyl alcohol	0.0665	Ethyl lactate	0.0690
<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol	0.0700	Acetophenone	0.1515
<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	0.0710	Pyridine	0.1125
<i>n</i> -Butyric acid	0.0670		

In the case of the first five solvents (Table II) the intrinsic viscosity remains practically constant, the variation being not more than 4 to 5%. But pyridine and acetophenone give values markedly different from those obtained with the five solvents mentioned above.

Intrinsic Viscosity and Temperature.—Various $\eta_{sp}/c - c$ curves for different temperatures with *n*-propyl alcohol, *n*-butyric acid and ethyl lactate as solvents become more and more parallel to the *c*-axis as the temperature is raised, the curve for *n*-propyl alcohol at 60° being almost parallel to the *c*-axis. The intrinsic viscosities at three different temperatures (extrapolated from the graph) are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Temp.	<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol.	<i>n</i> -Butyric acid.	Ethyl lactate.
40°	0.0693	0.0668	0.0680
50	0.0665	0.0641	0.0660
60	0.0630	0.0630	0.0644

The variation of intrinsic viscosity due to 10° rise in temperature is barely 4% (Table III).

The values of $[\eta]$ obtained from the curves $\eta_{sp}/c - c$ at various temperatures for pyridine and acetophenone are given in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Temp.	Intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ for solvents		
	Pyridine.	Acetophenone.	<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol with 5% H ₂ O.
30°	0.1120	0.1515	—
40	0.1050	0.0950	0.0832
50	0.1000	0.0650	0.0691
60	—	—	0.0610

The variation of $[\eta]$ with temperature is rather low for pyridine but quite considerable for acetophenone.

The variation of intrinsic viscosity with temperature in the case of *n*-propyl alcohol containing 5% water is shown in the last column of Table IV from which it is evident that the intrinsic viscosity at 40° is higher than that of pure *n*-propyl alcoholic solution (Table III) and the rate of variation of $[\eta]$ with temperature is also considerable.

Effect of Velocity Gradient.—The effects of different shearing stresses (i.e. different velocity gradients) on η/η_0 , i.e. relative viscosity in ethyl alcoholic solution are shown in Fig. 2, in which η/η_0 has been plotted against pressure expressed in cm. of water column. The curves for two different concentrations (1% and 10% solutions) of shellac are given. In the case of 1% solution fall in value

Fig. 2.

is rather small, becoming somewhat pronounced only at relatively high pressure. But in the case of a 10% solution there is a sharp fall with comparatively small increase in pressure, after which η/η_0 gradually approaches a constant value as the pressure is increased.

Syneresis of Gel.—Acetophenone solution of shellac at high concentrations can form gel showing the phenomenon of gel syneresis, as previously observed by Heller (*Compt. rend.*, 1937, 43, 204; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1941, 45, 1203; 1942, 46, 783) with the gels of ferric hydroxide, clay, etc. Thus when a 10% solution of shellac in acetophenone is prepared by warming, followed by cooling to 30°, it forms a thick gel, which on standing for 24 hours separates out into an upper sol phase and a lower concentrated gel phase. As the concentration of shellac is increased, the separation of the sol becomes less and less marked until at 40% concentration no further separation of sol and gel takes place even after 48 hours. The results are tabulated below (Table V).

TABLE V

Volume of solution taken = 20c.c.				
Conc. of shellac (%)	10	20	30	40
Separation of soln (c.c.)	12	10	5	Nil

These observations were made in wide bottles. When, however, 20 c. c. of the 10% solution were kept in a narrow test tube, the sol separation did not exceed 3 c. c. after 24 hours, which however, could be increased to 10 c. c. on centrifuging. Similar observations could also be made with gels in other solvents mentioned before, but owing to the greater solubility of shellac in such solvents gelation took place only at a much higher concentration, thus making a systematic study difficult. Synergetic phenomena have also been observed with urea-shellac gel (also observed by G. N. Bhattacharya in this laboratory) and shellac gel in acetone-water mixture.

DISCUSSION

There is a considerable volume of experimental data in the literature showing, without doubt, that a large number of macromolecular solutes dissolve in many solvents to the same kinetic units. Thus the observed constancy, as well as the low temperature coefficient of intrinsic viscosity of both organic and inorganic cellulose derivative; (Kraemer, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1938, 30, 1200; Sakurda and Shojino, *Kolloid Z.*, 1934, 68, 300; Kraemer and Sears, *J. Rheology*, 1931, 2, 29); Philippoff *Kautschuk*, 1938, 12, 124), led the authors to conclude that cellulose derivatives in dilute solutions dispersed to the same kinetic units. The same conclusion should apply to the first five solutions of shellac also (Table II), since it is highly improbable that these solutions, using different solvents, should contain a uniform size of the macromolecular aggregates and the same volume of solvents should be immobilised in every case. Moreover, as solvation and aggregation are very sensitive to changes of temperature, the negligible variation of $[\eta]$ with temperature in these cases may be regarded as a further confirmation of the molecularity of shellac in solution.

Apparent anomalies observed in cases of acetophenone and pyridine solutions, for which the values of intrinsic viscosity are markedly different from the constant value obtained in case of the other solvents, may be explained as follows: In the case of acetophenone, the low solubility of shellac in this solvent and also the readiness with which the system sets to a gel at as low a concentration as 10% suggest the existence of solvation and aggregation, which is further confirmed by the enormous temperature effect on the intrinsic viscosity. The existence of structure is also indicated by the fact that even at 2% concentration vigorous shaking causes a fall in η_{rel} from 1.316 to 1.225 as has been actually observed showing that mechanical stress has resulted in breakdown of the structure.

The case of pyridine is somewhat different. It will be observed from Table III that though the intrinsic viscosity is higher than in the case of other solvents, the effect of temperature on it is but slight. This may be attributed to the capacity of pyridine as a base to form salt with shellac that might disperse molecularly in dilute solution. This view is further supported by the following observation. When pyridine is added drop by drop to a 5% solution of shellac in propyl alcohol, the relative viscosity rises at first and ultimately attains a constant value, a fact that also receives explanation on the same basis, namely, that at first pyridine goes to form salt with shellac, thus causing a rise in viscosity, but ultimately when the salt formation is complete, the relative viscosity remains constant (*cf.* Bhattacharya, Bulletin No. 42, Indian Lac Research Institute, 1940).

A very interesting case of variation of intrinsic viscosity with temperature has been observed with *n*-propyl alcohol-water mixture, the variation being much higher than in the case of pure *n*-propyl alcohol. An explanation for this may be found in the solvation of shellac molecules with water as postulated by Palit, for solvation may be expected to diminish with temperature and thereby cause a fall in intrinsic viscosity. Further support of this view is obtained from the effect of addition of hydrochloric acid to shellac solution. It has been shown by Harris and Nagel (*Kolloid Z.*, 1923, 33, 248) that hydrochloric acid causes agglomeration of shellac which ultimately becomes insoluble in alcohol. In Fig. 3 is shown the effect of adding 5*N*-HCl to a 5% solution of

Fig. 3.

shellac in (i) *n*-propyl alcohol and (ii) in *n*-propyl alcohol—5% water mixture. In the former case the η/η_0 curve against volume of the acid rises continuously, presumably due to agglomeration. If, on the other hand, there be solvation of shellac in solution, then the effect of adding hydrochloric acid will be first to desolvate the particles and then to induce agglomeration, with the result that the curve η/η_0 against volume of HCl will first show a sharp fall and then a rise with increasing concentration of the acid. This is well illustrated by curve II in Fig. 3. These facts establish beyond doubt that the particles of shellac are solvated by water in solution.

In the case of 1% ethyl alcoholic solution (Fig. 2) the effect of pressure, *i.e.*, velocity gradient on viscosity is found to be slight in the low-pressure region, the solution behaving like a Newtonian liquid at first, but deviating from Newtonian behaviour at higher pressures. This, as proposed by Mark ("High Polymer", vol. II, p 271), is probably due to the particles being oriented during flow, the orientation being more pronounced at higher pressures. But the behaviour noticed in the case of 10% solution must be due to some other cause, namely, a change in structure arising from the mechanical stress; any structure that has been produced by the interaction of the dissolved particles, would be destroyed by stress (Freundlich and Seifriz, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1923, 104, 233). Hence the viscosity falls at first rapidly and ultimately assumes a constant value when the structure completely breaks down. Thus, we may assume that in a concentrated solution there is a some sort of association of the dissolved units which, however, does not proceed so far as to form a definite micelle.

Also the observed syneresis in the case of shellac gel may be interpreted on the assumption of the existence of structure in solution; of the two types of structure in solution postulated to explain syneresis, namely geloid and molecular, at lower concentration, the geloid species is unable to form close-net structure throughout the solution, and therefore settles down under the action of gravity. With increasing concentration of the solute, however, the geloid concentration progressively increases until at 40% (Table V) it is high enough to form a net-structure *en masse*. The peculiar behaviour of the solution in narrow tubes can be explained on the assumption that the gel structure is adsorbed on the surface and is thus prevented from settling down (Heller, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1942, 46, 783). When the gel is centrifuged, the centrifugal force greatly exceeds the surfaces; consequently the gel settles down.

All these facts go to show that though shellac dissolves molecularly in dilute solutions, which are most probably swarms or loose clusters, though not definite micelle, the difference between such clusters and micelle being that the colloidal micelle is a discrete entity, whereas the clusters exist only in a statistical sense, that is to say, they continually break down on account of

thermal agitation only to re-form to an average size. Decreased thermal agitation helps to form bigger and stabler clusters and these would account for the behaviour of shellac in concentrated solution.

The author is grateful to Dr. P. K. Bose, Director, Indian Lac Research Insitute, for his kind interest and constant encouragement throughout the course of the investigation.

INDIAN LAC RESEARCH INSTITUTE,
NANKUM, RANCHI.

Received March 13, 1946
